

THE EFFECT OF SIZING ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CF/BMI COMPOSITES UNDER HYGROTHERMAL CONDITION

Feng Tongbo, Zhao Yan*, Luo Yunfeng, Duan Yuexin, Zhang Zuoguang
School of Materials of Science and Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing, China
No. 37, Xueyuan Road, Haidian District, Beijing, 100191, China
jennyzhaoyan@buaa.edu.cn

Abstract

The flexural strength and ILSS of CCF300/QY8911 composites with different sizing on carbon fiber have been tested before and after they were immersed in distilled water at 71 °C for seven days. The absorption curves have been constructed. It can be found that the mechanical properties of CCF300/QY8911 are apparently affected by hygrothermal condition. The mechanical properties of CCF300/QY8911 with sizing A on the carbon fiber under hygrothermal condition have low quality.

Keywords: sizing; carbon fiber; BMI, composites; hygrothermal condition; mechanical property

1. Introduction

Carbon fibers with high modulus, high strength, low density and resistance to chemical environments have led to their wide spread use in many application. Carbon fibers are brittle which can be easily broken by passing over and through fiber handling devices which direct, spread, weave and braid the fiber bundles. The simple act of unwinding a fiber from a spool can result in damage.

Immediately after a surface treatment and drying, the fibers pass through an aqueous bath where they are coated with a sizing material which protects the fiber from damage. After the application of the water based material, the tow bundle is dried. Finally, the tows are wound on spools and packaged.

For recent reviews of carbon fiber technology, Paipetis and C. Galiotis [1] have investigated the micromechanics of reinforcement of a model composite consisting of continuous high-modulus fibre embedded in epoxy resin as a function of fibre sizing. The SEM examination of the fracture surfaces revealed clear interfacial failure for the unsized system whereas the sized system indicated areas of good adhesion. Yang Yu et al. [2] have discussed the effect of nano-silica modified sizing agent on the mechanical properties of CFRP, and good interfacial adhesion has been obtained due to the addition of nano-silica to sizing agent. Guan Rongbo et al. [3] have characterized the interfacial adhesion of unsized carbon fibre with different sizing agents and matrix via single fibre fragment test, and it was found that the sizing agents with more active groups improved the interfacial adhesion.

As far as our view, there are no open articles reporting the effect of sizing on mechanical properties of composites under hygrothermal condition. The stability of composites replying to water lies on that of its interface at a great level [4-6]. The compatibility between the sizing and the matrix materials becomes a crucial parameter in composites [7-9]. In this research work, the mechanical properties of CCF300/QY8911 composites affected by sizing under hygrothermal condition will be analyzed and the Scanning electron morphologies of CCF300/QY8911 composites will be characterized. In addition, the absorption curves will be checked.

2. Materials and experimental

For the preparation of composites, the QY8911 resin was used supplied by Beijing Aeronautical Manufacturing Technology Research Institute and the carbon fiber CCF300 was used as reinforcement supplied by Weihai Tuozhan Fiber Co. Ltd of China. In order to improve the compatibilization between the fibers and matrix, five different sizing agents which were numbered as A、B、C、D and E coated on CCF300 were employed supplied by Weihai Tuozhan Fiber Co. Ltd and Fudan university.

All unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced composites panels with fiber volume content of 60% were manufactured by autoclave processing at 85°C for 2hrs.

Five specimens of every sample with size of 84×12.5×2mm, which were dried

to constant weight in vacuum drying oven, were submerged in distilled water at 71° for 7 days in all-purpose hydraulic experiment machine INSTRON1811 produced by Instron Corporation. The specimens were weighted in the high precision balance, Mettler AE-260.

The content of water was calculated by the weight difference. The percent moisture content M defined as

$$M = \frac{W - W_d}{W_d} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Where W is the weight of moist material and W_d is the weight of dry specimens.

Both the flexural property and the ILSS

tests were performed in order to

determine the mechanical properties for interface and interlaminar of composites.

Flexural and ILSS tests were performed

both in the dry and the wet samples on

Instron 5500 testing machine at both

25° and 150° in order to determine the

influence of the water content in the

mechanical properties following the

ASTM D 7264 and ASTM D 2344 .

In order to understand better the effect of water on the composites structure, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) experiments were also performed.

3. Result and discussion

3.1 The absorption curves of CCF300/QY8911 composites

The amount of water absorbed in the CCF300/QY8911 composites with different sizing on the surface of carbon fibre was calculated by the weight difference between the samples exposed to water and the dried samples. Fig.1 shows the percentage of water absorbed plotted against time for all the samples. From Fig.1, it can be found that the CCF300 (A)/QY8911 had the highest absorption percentage comparing with others. In addition, there is no difference among CCF300/QY8911 composites samples with sizing B, C, D and E on the surface of carbon fibres.

Fig.1 Absorption curves of CCF300/QY8911 composites with different sizing on the surface of carbon fiber

3.2 The ILSS of CCF300/QY8911 composites

Mechanical tests were performed in all the samples before and after water absorption. Fig.2 and Fig.3 present these results. In general, the mechanical properties of these materials are decreased after the moisture uptake, due to the effect of water molecules, which change the structure and properties of the interface between fibers and matrix.

Water absorption and their resulting effects contribute to the loss of compatibilization between fibers and matrix, which results in debonding and weakening of the interface adhesion.

Fig.2 ILSS of CCF300/QY8911 composites with different sizing on the surface of carbon fibre

From Fig.2, it can be found that the ILSS of composites with or without water decreased under high temperature and the temperature is very important to the shear properties of the composites. The preserving ratios of ILSS of dry CCF300/QY8911 are over 50% when the testing temperature is at 150°. In other way, the ratios of wet CCF300/QY8911 composites are around 80% when the testing temperature is at 25°. Especially when the wet composites were tested at 150°, the preserving ratios of ILSS of CCF300/QY8911 decline mightily at about 25% and even for CCF300 (A)/QY8911, ratio is nothing more than 18%. Taking one with another, the descending level of ILSS of CCF300 (A)/QY8911 is the greatest. The hygrothermal condition affects the ILSS of composites remarkably, and the

influence of temperature is more apparent than water.

3.3 The flexural strength of CCF300/QY8911 composites

From Fig.3, it can be found the flexural strength of composites changed much coming along the temperature. For the dry composites, the preserving ratios of flexural strength are about 70% tested at 150°. In addition, for the wet composites, the preserving ratios of flexural strength are nearly 40% tested at 150°. The lowest one is CCF300 (A)/QY8911. Contrarily the preserving ratios of flexural strength of wet composites are nearly 100% under testing temperature at 25°. The temperature plays a very important role in flexural strength. Considering the wet condition only, the flexural strength of composites is hardly influenced by water. The influence of temperature is remarkable, and the combined effect of temperature and water causes a considerable reduction of the flexural strength.

Fig. 3 Flexural strength of CCF300/QY8911

composites with different sizing on the surface of carbon fibre

As a result, it can be found that the mechanical properties of CCF300/QY8911 with sizing A on the carbon fiber CCF300 are greatly affected by hydrothermal condition, and its preserving ratios are the lowest.

Fig.4 shows the CCF300 (A)/QY8911 composite structure before and after water absorption, where the loss of adhesion between fiber and matrix, characterized by the apparition of voids

can be noticed.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig.4 SEM photographs for CCF300

(A)/QY8911 composite before (a) and (b) and after (c) and (d) hydrothermal at 71° (the (a) and (c) are cross section; the (b) and (d) are section plane)

4. Conclusions

Firstly, the CCF300/QY8911 with sizing A covered on carbon fibre had the highest absorption percentage. Then the

flexural strength of CCF300/QY8911 composites was affected by the effect of water and temperature together and especially influenced by temperature. In the end, both water and temperature affected the results of ILSS of CCF300/QY8911 and the reducing level is greater than that of flexural properties. On all accounts, the mechanical properties of CCF300/QY8911 composites with sizing A on the carbon fiber under hygrothermal condition have low quality.

References

- [1] A. Paipetis and C. Galiotis, Composites Part A 21A (1996) 755-161.
- [2] Yang Yu et al., New Carbon Materials, 20 (2005) 211-216.
- [3] Guan Rongbo et al., Fiber Composites, 1 (2002) 23-26.
- [4] Wu Yunqigige, Hi-Tech Fiber and Application, 29 (2004) 24-25.
- [5] Zhang Deqing and Wei Yuezhen, Journal of Qiqihar University, 16 (2000) 6-8.
- [6] Li Xiangyang et al., Acta Materialiae Compositae Sinica, 17 (2000) 111-113.
- [7] Huang Tao and Jiao Guiqiong, Structure and Environment Engineering, 33 (2006) 45-48.
- [8] Wang Xiaojie et al., Journal of Solid Rocket Technology, 29 (2006) 301-304.
- [9] Ren Huitao et al., Journal of Building Materials, 8 (2005) 520-525.